

COMPRESSIBILITY OF CHOPPED FIBRE-REINFORCED PREPREGS DURING COMPRESSION MOULDING

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to investigate the compressibility, and the pore kinetics and kinematics during compression moulding of low and high fibre content thermoset prepregs. Three-dimensional tomography images of the evolving mesostructures of these prepregs were obtained by performing interrupted *in situ* compression tests using a specially designed compression rheometer. The pore size distribution and shapes were determined using these images. During compression, the high fibre content prepreg exhibited consolidation and segregation, whereas during relaxation the compression stress was not totally released. The origin of the consolidation mechanism could be attributed to the initial large amount of open pores that disappeared during compression, suggesting that gases contained in pores flowed out of the prepreg. For the low fibre content prepreg, the flow was much less compressible. Porosity was low and mostly closed. Pores only progressively disappeared during compression. The origin of this mechanism could be attributed to gas dissolution mechanisms in the matrix. The origin of the difference in the relaxation behaviour could be related to the large difference in fibre content between both prepregs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their excellent properties and their cost effectiveness, thermoset prepregs are widely used in automotive industry to manufacture body and semi-structural parts. The considered thermoset prepregs are semi products composed of a thermoset matrix reinforced with 25 mm to 50 mm long and chopped fibre bundles. Various thermoset polymeric matrices (polyesters, vinylesters, epoxy) and fibrous reinforcements (glass, carbon, biosourced fibres) are used to fabricate composite parts [1]. Generally, the fibre content ranges from 15wt% to 25 wt%. However, higher fibre content formulations (40-60 wt%) are being in development for fabricating structural parts with enhanced mechanical properties. Chopped thermoset prepregs are produced in the form of 1 to 3 mm thick sheets that can be easily cut and handled. The sheet processing consists of three steps: (i) paste mixing, (ii) impregnation of the fibre network by the thermoset polymer paste and calendaring, and (iii) paste thickening and storage [1]. During stage (i), pores can be entrapped in the polymer paste during mixing of paste ingredients [2]. After stage (ii), the “initial” porosity of prepregs ϕ_{p0} is approximately 5-10% [3-4]. The initial porosity reaches up to 40% for higher fibre volume fractions ϕ_0 .

Thermoset prepregs are commonly formed using compression moulding [1]. This process consists in (i) squeezing stacked sheets inside a hot (approximately 150°C) mould at closing speeds that range from 1 to 10 mm.s⁻¹, (ii) curing the polymeric matrix for 1 to 3 min in the closed mould. Several challenges are encountered in optimising compression moulding of thermoset prepregs. Among them,

understanding and modelling pore transport and decrease/increase is a critical issue [2]. In the absence of proper description and model of pore kinetics and kinematics, thermoset prepregs are generally modelled as incompressible materials [3-6]. This is a very strong *a priori* assumption when considering the aforementioned initial pore content ϕ_{p0} . The compressibility of thermoset prepregs, and its correlation with the pore kinetics and kinematics, was scarcely investigated for compression moulded prepregs [7]. For example, the compressibility of prepregs was shown to be significant during the early stage of compression [8-10].

To complete these aforementioned works, the objective of this study was to investigate the compressibility, and the pore kinetics and kinematics during compression moulding of low and high fibre content thermoset prepregs. For that purpose, a compression rheometer was specially designed and mounted inside a laboratory X-ray microtomograph. This device enabled rheometry experiments to be performed while scanning prepregs at different stages of compression. This method also enabled 3D *in situ* images of the evolving mesostructures to be reconstructed. The pore size distribution and shape were determined using these images. These original mesoscale structural data, combined with the macroscale stresses and strains measurements that were simultaneously recorded during compression tests enabled a relevant analysis of the early stages of compression of prepregs.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two industrial thermoset prepregs were used. The first prepreg, denoted LF in the following sections, consisted of a polyester-based paste that was reinforced with 25 wt% glass fibre bundles. The second prepreg, denoted HF, was a vinylester-based paste reinforced with 50 wt% glass fibre bundles. Compression samples were made of two stacked discs with a 20 mm diameter. The initial height h_0 was approximately 4 and 6 mm for the HF and LF samples, respectively.

Fig. 1: *In situ* compression setup installed in the 3SR lab X-ray microtomograph [9].

Both samples were subjected to simple compression at room temperature. For that purpose, they were placed inside a compression cell that was specially designed to enable 3D *in situ* imaging of the samples and their porous mesostructures using a X-ray microtomograph (3SR Lab, Grenoble, France, RX solutions) [11] (Fig.1). The compression cell was equipped with a load sensor with a maximum loading capacity of 7.5 kN, which enabled the compression force F to be measured during compression tests. The nominal compression stress $\sigma_0 = F/S_0$ was calculated, S_0 being the initial compression surface of the samples. The force was exerted on the samples by the relative motion of

two parallel compression plates which was achieved using an electromechanical actuator (maximal translation velocity of 100 m min^{-1}). A LVDT sensor was used to measure the vertical motion u of the plates for determining the (i) the actual height h of the deformed samples, *i.e.*, $h \approx h_0 + u$, (ii) and the compression Hencky strain $\varepsilon_h = \ln(h/h_0)$.

Compression experiments were performed using plates that were coated with silicone grease to avoid friction effects. The compression velocity was $100 \mu\text{m min}^{-1}$. At various compression strains ε_h , samples were subjected to a 2 min relaxation (up to a stabilisation of σ_0) and 3D images of the samples were recorded. During scanning, 1500 X-ray radiographs of samples were taken over 360° at a spatial resolution of $17 \mu\text{m}$ (acceleration voltage: 80 kV, intensity $370 \mu\text{A}$, scanning time 20 min). These radiographs were used to reconstruct 32 bit grey scale 3D images. Then, these images were resized into 8-bit grey images to facilitate the image analysis.

Fig. 2: Principle of thresholding method. (a,b) Initial image slices of HF and LF prepreps, respectively. (b,c) Histograms of the images restricted to the region of interest (ROI). (e,f) Examples of thresholded slices of 3D images.

Standard image analysis was conducted using the software ImageJ. The matrix and the fibre phases were separated from the pore phase (Fig. 2) using a standard thresholding operation restricted to a region of interest (ROI). Then, the pore volume fraction ϕ was calculated by counting the number of

black pixels (corresponding to the pore phase) and dividing it by the total number of voxels of the ROI:

The plugin “3D Granulometry” [12-13] of ImageJ was used to perform an analysis of the pore size distribution. This plugin computes series of morphological opening and closing operations using octahedron structural elements of increasing size [14]. The granulometry function maps the size of each structuring element to the number of pixels that are removed during opening operations.

The plugin “BoneJ” [15] of ImageJ was also used to perform connectivity analysis on the porosity phase. This plugin enabled us to identify and remove the closed pores within the images. This plugin was used to determine the amount of closed and open pores in the samples.

The images were also used to perform a precise analysis of the height of the samples (Fig.1), and the surface S of the samples was measured using the ImageJ function “wand”. Using this data, the surface (ε_S) and volumetric (ε_V) strains were defined as follows:

$$\varepsilon_S = \ln\left(\frac{S(t)}{S_0}\right); \varepsilon_V = \ln\left(\frac{V(t)}{V_0}\right) = \varepsilon_h + \varepsilon_S. \quad (1)$$

For strain calculations, all the geometrical parameters were the average of ten measurements.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 3: Evolutions of as functions of the axial compression strain of the compression stress (a,b) and volumetric and surface strains (c,d) for the HF (a,c) and LF (b,d) prepregs.

The evolution of the stress σ_0 as a function of the deformation ε_h is shown in Fig. 3 for the two tested prepregs. This figure shows a significant difference between the strains calculated using the compression device measurements and the strains calculated using the 3D images. This effect is related to the deformability of the compression device. Therefore, in the following section, all the strains ε_h were calculated only from 3D images. The figure also shows that the two prepregs exhibit different mechanical behaviours. The stress drops also observed in the figure are mainly related to the sample relaxation. As evident from this figure, the HF prepregs did not totally release the compression stress, suggesting an elastic deformation stored in its highly entangled fibre network. On the contrary, the relaxation of LF prepreg was total for compression strains below $\varepsilon_h = -0.6$. For axial strains

below -0.6 , the sample reached the side walls of the compression cell, preventing a total stress relaxation. The figure also proves that the compression stress was also much higher for the HF prepreg than for the LF prepreg, *i.e.*, approximately 9 MPa and 0.5 MPa at $\varepsilon_h = -0.4$, respectively. Note also that fibre-matrix segregation was observed during the HF prepreg compression. This phenomenon probably occurred because of the low strain compression strain rate and the high connectivity of the HF fibre network. This phenomenon was not observed for the LF prepreg.

Fig. 3 shows the evolution of ε_S and ε_V as a function of ε_h for both prepregs. Obviously, the HF prepreg is very compressible. During its compression, large consolidation occurred as its volumetric strain ε_V decreased to -0.2 , whereas its surface strain ε_S reached 0.25. The evolution of ε_V and ε_S could be divided into two stages. Up to $\varepsilon_h = -0.15$, ε_S was weak (the surface of the sample was almost constant), whereas the volumetric strain ε_V exhibited a sharp decrease. Then, ε_S increased and ε_V exhibited a slower decrease. As evident from Fig. 3, the behaviour of the LF prepreg is different. In this case, the volumetric strain ε_V does not exhibit significant evolution. Thus, LF prepreg is not as compressible as HF prepreg.

Fig. 4 shows the evolution of total porosity as a function of ε_h as well as the evolution of closed and open porosities. The initial total porosity was very different for HF and LF prepregs, 0.18 and 0.02, respectively. For HF prepreg, almost all the total porosity corresponded to an open porosity in the initial state. As shown in this figure, the total porosity of the HF prepreg exhibited a sharp decrease up to $\varepsilon_h = -0.35$. Below this value, the total porosity showed a slighter decrease, suggesting potential changes in the pore decrease mechanisms. Up to $\varepsilon_h = -0.35$, the open porosity followed the same trend as the total porosity, and progressively disappeared. The closed porosity followed a more complex trend. First, it exhibited a slight increase, suggesting that a part of the open porosity was closed during compression. Finally, it exhibited a progressive decrease down to 0.01. The evolution of the porosity of LF prepreg was different. The decrease in the total porosity mostly corresponded to a decrease in the closed porosity. The open porosity was very low for this prepreg, and disappeared for a compression below $\varepsilon_h = -0.1$. The difference in the relative amount of open and closed porosities in HF and LF prepregs suggests different pore decrease mechanisms. For the HF prepreg, the large amount of open porosity implies that the gases that were contained in the open pores could easily flow out of this prepreg, whereas the decrease in porosity in the LF prepreg could be attributed to dissolution of gases that were contained in the pores in the prepreg matrix. The pores could also reach a size too small to be measured because of the resolution of the X-ray images.

Fig. 4: Evolution of the total, closed and open porosities during compression for the HF (a) and LF (b) prepregs. Images correspond to the upper view of 3D representation of the total porous phase.

Fig. 4 also shows slices of 3D images of the pore phase in HF and LF prepregs. The pores of the HF prepregs were visually flat, and predominantly located between fibre layers. The pores of LF prepregs were thicker and less flat, probably because of the low fibre content of this prepreg, which could allow them to expand isotropically during prepreg processing.

Fig.5 shows the probability distribution function of the pore size for both prepregs as well as the evolution of the peak porosity size as a function of the compression strain. Note that, as the pores were rather flat, *i.e.*, anisotropic, the pore size determined using octahedron structural elements should rather be representative of the pore thickness. The evolution of this descriptor shows that a progressive pore flattening occurred for the HF prepreg: the peak of the distribution progressively moved towards a pore size of approximately $60\ \mu\text{m}$ (Figs. 5(a) and 5(c)) during the compression. For the LF prepreg, distributions are less sharp (Fig. 5(b)), and the peak porosity size showed a significant and regular decrease with the increase in the compression strain.

Fig. 5: Pore size distribution at various strains for (a) HF prepregs and (b) LF prepregs. (c) Evolution of the peak pore size as a function of the compression strain for HF and LF prepregs.

4 CONCLUSION

The compressibility and the related mesostructural evolution of a low and a high fibre content thermoset prepregs were studied during compression. For that purpose, original experiments were performed using a compression device inside a laboratory X-ray microtomograph. This device enabled interrupted *in situ* lubricated compression tests to be performed, whereas 3D images of the deforming prepregs were acquired. The evolutions of several structural descriptors of the mesostructure of prepregs, such as the pore volume fraction and size distribution, were determined using image analysis procedures. Both prepregs exhibited great differences in their structural properties, and their rheological behaviour. The high fibre content prepreg was extremely compressible, especially during the early stage of compression. Segregation phenomenon between the matrix and the fibre phases was also observed during compression. This large consolidation and segregation effect could be attributed to the closing of the large amount of open and highly anisotropic pores in this prepreg. Interrupting tests showed that the relaxation of the compression stress was not complete suggesting elastic deformation stored in the fibrous network during compression and not released upon relaxation. The low fibre content prepreg was less compressible, probably both because of a lower initial pore content

and because most of its pores were closed. For this prepreg, pores slowly disappeared during compression. This phenomenon could be attributed to a progressive dissolution of gases contained in the pores in the polymer matrix. Further, the relaxation was total and no segregation phenomenon occurred, suggesting a lower effect of the fibre network in this prepreg compared to the high fibre content prepreg. These original experimental provide guidelines for developing new constitutive relations for the rheology of compressible composite materials.

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